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Final report of WP8

Executive Summary

Adding new members and partnerships is essential to develop BBMRI capacity and exploit its full potential as an enabler of health research. The aim of WP8 is to expand the number of BBMRI-ERIC member countries, both belonging to the European Research Area and outside the European Union. Throughout the duration of ADOPT, BBMRI-ERIC WP8 was responsible for the key activities necessary to identify and engage with possible new members. In particular, WP8 mapped candidate countries and led the negotiations with candidate member states of BBMRI-ERIC. This workflow was managed in parallel with deliverable 8.2, which allowed the organisation of 4 workshops in key regions of interest for BBMRI-ERIC (China, Africa, Middle-East, North and South America); the workshops facilitated cooperation with new international partners and opened up new opportunities for Membership or Observership.

As a result, Poland, Latvia and Bulgaria joined as Members, and Cyprus as an Observer. All pre-ADOPT observerships (IARC, Turkey, Switzerland) were renewed in 2018. Lithuania and Spain are foreseen to join in 2020.

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Document log

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Background

Cancer, Alzheimer, rare diseases and other health challenges of our time know no border. So should EU and global research efforts. European research infrastructures like BBMRI provide the framework for the creation of the European Research Area, that can enable the level of international collaboration required to fight health challenges of the present and the future.

During the preparatory phase of the creation of BBMRI-ERIC, almost all EU countries expressed their interest to join BBMRI. However, when BBMRI was finally established only 18 countries became full members. Adding new members and partnerships is essential to develop BBMRI capacity and exploit its full potential as an enabler of health research.

The goal of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC is to provide comprehensive information to set up a framework for global Research Infrastructures in the life sciences, building on existing initiatives and networks, and to facilitate the cooperation with European counterparts. To support the overall goal, the work within ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC WP8 can be roughly divided into two aims: firstly, enlarging the membership of BBMRI-ERIC (tasks 1 and 2) and secondly, developing collaborations outside the EU or Europe (tasks 3, 4 and 5).

1. Approaches (Methods)

WP8 provided the resources to start collaborating with non-European biobanks and networks as well as increase national membership of BBMRI-ERIC (i.e. new National Nodes) by supporting conferences and workshops in the regions of interest as well as funding fact-finding missions to those countries for membership negotiations.

During the ADOPT Steering Committee Meetings (BBMRI-ERIC Management Committee) the National Node directors were informed about the progress of WP8. The work is divided into two main aims:

- enlarging the membership of BBMRI-ERIC in EU/Europe;
- developing collaborations outside EU/Europe.

WP8 was developed in close collaboration with existing BBMRI-ERIC member states: a series of workshops were co-organised and if possible co-funded as well as many National Node directors were invited to present in these workshops.

Enlarging the membership of BBMRI-ERIC in EU/Europe

Within the first period of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC the country mapping was executed (Task 1) in order to identify countries for future membership (see deliverable report D8.1). This was mainly done by reviewing and analysing national research infrastructures' strategies (often called "roadmaps" following the ESFR1 nomenclature). The challenge was that these roadmaps were often published only in local languages, and therefore needed to be translated. This task was executed during summer 2016 and published as a presentation during EBW2016.

The results of the country mapping informed the BBMRI-ERIC strategy to enlarge its membership, helped to discuss advantages and helped with evaluation of such decisions with candidate members (Task 2). Workshops with key scientists from candidate member states were organized within Global

Biobank Week 2017 in Stockholm and within the BBMRI-ERIC Forum seminar and RI conference in Sofia for the Bulgarian presidency from 20-24 March 2018.

The discussions and negotiations with new countries are an ongoing activity of BBMRI-ERIC. Currently, BBMRI-ERIC is negotiating (to different degrees) with Lithuania, Romania and Spain.

Developing collaborations outside EU/Europe

Biobanking activities and their challenges are not restricted to the EU or Europe. Therefore, collaborations need to be developed beyond these borders. Involving new biobanks and biobankers especially from outside Europe takes the necessary time and is also ongoing with focusing on China, Africa and low-/middle-income countries, North & South America, and the MENA.

In total 4 workshops were organized: EuroMed workshop in Malta for the MENA Region, the IARC – BCNet – BBMRI-ERIC – Training in Biobanking for Pathologists and Pathology / Histology Technicians (22-23 May 2017) for Africans, workshop and Symposium in Izmir for the Middle East and lastly, a workshop was organized for Latin American biobankers in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

2. Results

Within the first period of the project, 3 countries joined BBMRI-ERIC: Poland and Latvia as Members, as well as Cyprus as an Observer. During the second period Bulgaria joined BBMRI-ERIC. According to the Statutes of BBMRI-ERIC, observership has to be renewed every three years. All observerships (IARC, Turkey, Switzerland, Cyprus) were renewed in 2018.

It is likely that Lithuania and Spain will commence negotiations and possibly join in 2020. Lithuania has submitted an informal request to join. Delegates from the Spanish ministry of science have expressed their willingness to join, but due to EU and national elections, a governmental position could not be reached yet, but will be discussed in the future.

The work carried out has helped BBMRI-ERIC to involve new and more countries and widen the services offered. With workshops and seminars, scientists and other stakeholders from new countries but also regions have learned about our activities and how BBMRI-ERIC can help them in their research projects.

The workshops raised significant interest in the services of BBMRI-ERIC, raising the global profile of BBMRI as well as European Research Infrastructure Consortia in general. Such interest was demonstrated in terms of direct requests from the scientific community to work out solutions for researchers outside of Europe to access (in part, or full) BBMRI-ERIC services.

3. Next Steps

BBMRI-ERIC will continue to invest resources and time to facilitate the enlargement of BBMRI-ERIC, by updating the mapping of candidate countries, and monitoring the development/update of national research infrastructures roadmaps, to identify new countries with a specific interest in biobanking. BBMRI-ERIC will also keep promoting biobanking at the global level, therefore attempting to influence national research infrastructure strategies to consider establishing BBMRI-ERIC National Nodes.

Thanks to ADOPT, BBMRI-ERIC managed to attract considerable interest from non-EU countries, which are willing to become BBMRI-ERIC members and/or formalise strong collaborations (e.g. Japan, Qatar, Brazil and Argentina). However, the ERIC regulation and the BBMRI-ERIC statute currently limits the type and quality of international collaboration possible with non-EU countries.

During the Steering Committee meeting on 20 March 2019 in Brussels it was unanimously decided that BBMRI-ERIC HQ will investigate possible solutions to enhance international cooperation, and report to the Assembly of Members meeting on 12 June 2019 in Vienna. BBMRI-ERIC will investigate the opportunity to create new membership models (alternative to the full member or observer currently available) that can maintain the governance balance existing within BBMRI-ERIC, while fulfilling the needs/requirements of non-EU countries. BBMRI-ERIC will consult with various stakeholders (non-EU members' ministries of research, other ERICs with international members, ERIC Forum, ESFRI, etc.) to get best practices/success stories in international cooperation.

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